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Organizational Climate and Work Engagement

Damianus Abun ^(a) Carmelita A. Serrano ^(b) Janette R. Lazaro ^(c)

a) PhD: Professor, School of Business and Accountancy, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.

b) MBA: Senior Instructor, School of Business and Accountancy, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.

c) PhD: Professor, School of Arts, Sciences and Education, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.

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ABSTRACT

Organizational climate is the barometer of work engagement. The study aimed to determine the correlation between organizational climate and employees' work engagement. To strengthen the theory of the study, related literature was reviewed. The study used a descriptive correlational research design. Questionnaires were utilized for the data. The population of the study was the employees of the colleges in the Ilocos Region. Weighted mean was used to determine the average mean of the dimensions of both the organizational climate and work engagement, while Pearson r Correlation was used to determine the correlation between the organizational climate and work engagement of the employees. The result of the Pearson r correlation indicates that there is a significant correlation between organizational climate and the work engagement of employees. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

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Introduction

The issue of business nowadays is competition and to win, one must have the necessary strategy to play the game and win big (Wilson, 2012). Part of the game plan is human resources that have the necessary skills or experience to play or to work, otherwise, they need to be sent for further training (Kenton, & Anderson, 2020). Climate affects the temperature of the organization which eventually affects the employees' behavior, motivation, and work engagement (Chaudhary, et.al., 2013, Sunarsih & Helmiatin, 2017, Sambandam & Chockalingam, 2019).

This research is concerned with the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. Issues such as clarity, responsibility, flexibility, rewards, and teamwork are intangible elements of the organization that managers should not neglect because it affects the motivation of employees to work (Drigo Consulting Group, 2003,

* Corresponding author. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9693-1541

Hay Group, 2003). After the researcher has been working with schools for 25 years, he has seen one aspect of management function that has been overlooked: organizational climate management.

There have been a few research works done along with the organizational climate of the schools such as Hoy (2020), on school climate and outcomes namely, Thomas (1976), on the dimensions of school climate, and Batlolona (2018) on the school climate and teachers' performance improvement. Hence, this study investigated the organizational climate of the schools and how it affects the work engagement of the employees. The results may help the management revise policies that can promote a better-working climate such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment (Hey Group Research, 2003).

The study is divided into several parts. The first part presents the rationale and objectives of the study. The second part is the related literature review that discusses the theories of the study. The third part is the methodology. This part discusses the research design, population of the study, its locale, research instruments, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is the empirical data analysis and the findings of the study. The final part covers the results and its conclusion.

Literature Review

The purpose of the literature review is to gain an understanding of the current topic based on what other researchers and authors have found or discussed. This is to help the researcher gain more knowledge or understanding about the topic investigated (Western Sydney University, 2017).

Organizational Climate

Organizational climate refers to employees' perceptions of organizational practices reported by people who work there (Rousseau, 20003). It is a situational characteristic that links to the thoughts and feelings of workers that shape the common perception of employees as a result of organizational policies and procedures (Miller, 2003). Similarly, Insel and Moos (1972) claimed that it is a psychological and social dimension of the environment, including people's perceptions.

Catto (2001) as cited in Evans, et.al (2007) contended that organizational climate is the result of organizational practices. According to Rousseau (1988), it is caused by several dimensions such as communication, conflicts (functional and dysfunctional), leadership (consistency, inconsistency, direction), and reward system. These aspects make up the organizational climate. A positive climate means that communication, leadership, relationships, and reward system are functioning well. On the contrary, it is an indication that those dimensions are not handled properly by the management.

Rousseau (1988) argued that a stressful organizational climate may happen if there is limited participation in decision-making, and use of punishment, and in a study of organizational climate, a common perceptual agreement among employees in the organization was greatly considered (Glick, 1985).

Leadership and Organizational Climate

Studies have found that organizational climate is a logical consequence of management and leadership (Stringer, 2002, Ko & Kang, 2019, Dulay, et.al., 2015). Clarity, responsibility, rewards, standards, support, and commitment can result in an organizational climate (Stringer, 2002). These are also dimensions pointed out by Hay Group (2003) that contribute to organizational climate. According to Hay Group's (2003) research, 70 % of the employee's perception of organizational climate is a direct result of their manager's leadership styles. They further said that one of the most significant strengths of an effective leader is the ability to create a positive work climate. This has been confirmed by several studies such as Ko and Kang (2019), Dulay and Karadag (2015), and Likert (1967) that different leadership styles affect the organizational climate.

Stringer (2002), Allen (2003) and Cameron and Smart (1998) are all arguing that a positive organizational climate is a direct result of effective leadership. The same point is also stressed by Yuan and Lee (2011) that producing high performance, satisfying, and healthy work climate depends heavily on how managers go about leading employees. The climate that employees feel is not separated from the leadership itself.

The Effect of Organizational Climate on Performance

Hay Group's (2003) study consistently found that when workers are enabled and motivated, they provide their best effort. Such a finding is also confirmed by the study of Denis and Coban, (2016, cited in Hirlak, et.al 2018). Denis and Coban (2016) as cited in Hirlak, et.al (2018) showed that organizational climate produces emotions that may affect the commitment of employees toward the organization. Therefore, they suggested that this should be designed to maximize organizational performance. Hirlak, et.al, (2018) also found that the sub-dimensions of organizational climate such as support, cohesion, intrinsic recognition, impartiality, and pressure have a positive and significant effect on employee creativity; while cohesion pressure, intrinsic recognition, and employee creativity have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

James and Jones (1977) as cited in Kopelman, et.al (1990) and Putter (2010) have mentioned that organizational climate is tied to organizational productivity, profitability, sustainability, growth, and work engagement which is a function of an individual's behavior and according to Kopelman (1990) that there are three behaviors pertinent to organizational climate such as attachment, performance and citizen-related. Danisha's (2017) study also confirmed the correlation between organizational climate and employees' performance in the chemical industry in India. Waktola (2014) mentioned several dimensions such as trust, support, autonomy, fairness, reward, and teamwork motivate employees' commitment to the organization. Interestingly, support, and teamwork have the highest contribution. This is also shown by the study of Chaudhary, et.al (2014) that organizational climate improves the work engagement of employees. The correlation between organizational climate and performance is not only applied in manufacturing companies but even in educational institutions as Palash and Deepak (2017) proved in their study.

Dimensions of Organizational Climate

Drigo Consulting Group (2003) has argued that organizational climate is a set of measurable properties of the work environment that are perceived by the people who live and work in it and influence their behavior and motivation. According to this group, several dimensions of organizational climate have been considered to significantly impact the company's bottom line and these are flexibility, responsibility, standards, rewards, clarity, and team commitment. The same dimensions are also recommended by Hey Group (2003).

Clarity dimension

It will not be considered an overstatement if Gore (2017) contended that the most important competency for a leader to possess is clarity. He considered clarity as the greatest strategic advantage that an organization can have. Clarity simply means clearness, lucidity, and freedom from ambiguity. Hey Group (2003) viewed that clarity means that employees understand their organization's mission and of their department and their unit contribution to achieving the common vision-mission. Thus, leadership or management needs to communicate the strategic direction of the organization as well as the direction of the department and its function (Gore, 2017).

Standard Dimension

Cen and Cenelec (2013) claimed that many businesses use standards in their daily operation because it helps the business ensure the quality and safety of the products or services that entails satisfying customers' satisfaction.

Concerning the organizational climate, standards mean the measurement to be used to gauge the quality of work or the output that is expected of employees on a day-to-day basis. In other words, employees are expected to come out with the output daily to be measured against the established standards.

Individual Responsibility Dimension

Organizational performance will always depend on individual responsibility. Litwin (1967) pointed out individual responsibility as one of the dimensions of organizational climate. What he meant by individual responsibility is individual freedom in carrying out their duties and responsibilities without external coercion. In other words, managers must give employees the freedom to decide, work, and exercise their authority in their areas of responsibility. Freedom or autonomy is experienced in two ways: first, the employees have the proper decision-making power in their jobs. Second, employees are encouraged to be creative in finding ways that may lead to new, cheaper, and more efficient ways of doing things. This can also mean that the sole responsibility of the work is given to the employees and therefore there should be no interference from the management related to the work of employees (Balachandran & Thomas, 2007). This not only allows autonomy to grow with the employees but also helps to reduce the burdens of the top management.

Flexibility Dimension

Rosen (n.d) defines organizational flexibility as adaptability, openness, and intensity at which an organism adapts to its changing environment. This is the only way to compete with other organizations. Along this line, LaMarco (2018), a management expert contends that rigidity can fail the organization because of the rapid changes in technology and the economy. Managers must be brave enough to violate the rules of policies when those policies are a hindrance to development. In this study, flexibility dimensions of climate measured employees' perceptions about the institution's desire to adapt to changes and employees' creativity.

Reward and Recognition Dimension

Commonly, the reward is referring to monetary incentives given to employees because of good performance (Foronda, 2010). This is one of the strategies of companies to attract good talents and motivate employees to perform better. Employees are motivated when they know that their efforts are rewarded and consequently it reinforces their good performance. While recognition is referring to intangible things in nature and is not related to monetary value. This can be simple praise from management for an employee who has done a great job. However, these two terms are always used together: there should also be emotional touch through praise or kind words accompanying the monetary rewards and advancement opportunities given to those who perform beyond standards.

Team Commitment Dimension

Wooly, et.al, 2015, cited in Ludden, (2016) and her colleagues from Carnegie Mellon University found that “the intelligence of a group can exceed that of its members if the right conditions are met. They stated that collective intelligence predicts performance (Ludden, 2016, cited from Wooly, et.al, 2015).

The team dimension of organizational climate measures the feeling of everyone who works cooperatively to accomplish the goals (Hey Group, 2003, cited in Foronda, 2010). In this case, everyone works together to accomplish the team’s goals (Heathfield, 2019).

Work Engagement

Work engagement is about the cognitive, physical, and emotional or psychological connection to the work (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). These are the kinds of employees who are absorbed by their work as they are highly engaged and deliver quality performance (Bakker & Leiter, 2010).

On one hand, one group says that work engagement is a single construct such as Maslach and Leiter (1997) as cited by Kuok and Taormina, (2017). On the other hand, it is a multidimensional construct (Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzalez-Roma & Bakker, 2002). This study considers work engagement as a multidimensional construct. This is another development to the researcher’s previous studies related to work engagement as an emotional state and physical engagement sans the cognitive aspect (Abun, et.al, 2017).

Conceptual Framework

Source: Hey Group (2003) and Drigo Consulting Group (2003) and Kuok and Taormina (2017)

Figure 1: The framework is a correlation study which means the independent variable may affect the dependent variable (Thomas, 2020). In this case, when the independent variables are changed or manipulated, then consequently the dependent variables change (McLeod, 2019). The conceptual framework of the current study reflects the correlation between the two variables, organizational climate and work engagement of the employee.

Statement of the Problems

The purpose of the study is to investigate the correlation between the two variables, organizational climate and work engagement of employees. It specifically answered the following questions:

- 1. What is the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of**
 - 1.1 clarity;*
 - 1.2 standards;*
 - 1.3 individual responsibility;*
 - 1.4 flexibility;*
 - 1.5 reward and recognition; and*
 - 1.6 team commitment?*
- 2. What is the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of**
 - 2.1 cognitive engagement;*
 - 2.2 effective engagement; and*
 - 2.3 conative engagement?*
- 3. Is there a relationship between organizational climate and the work engagement of employees?**

Assumption

The study assumed that the work climate affects the work engagement of employees and can be measured. The questionnaires in gathering the data for the study are valid and the responses of the employees are honest and objective.

Hypothesis

Organizational climate plays an important role in supporting work engagement as Raja, et.al.(2019) pointed out that a good climate is a prerequisite for the success of the organization. Therefore, the study hypothesizes that organizational climate correlates with the work engagement of employees.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study was limited to the faculty and employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region and it covered only six dimensions of organizational climate as prescribed by Hey Group Research (2003) such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment and three dimensions of work engagement which are cognitive, affective, and conative dimensions.

Research Methodology

The research methodology is the specific procedures to be followed in investigating. This is the basis for the determination of the quality and validity of the research (Wilkinson & Birmingham, 2003). Along with such a concept, this part presents the methodology of how this study was conducted or carried out.

Research Design

The study used a descriptive assessment and correlational research design to determine the level of organizational climate and its effect on the work engagement of employees. Ariola (2006) contended that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. (McCombes, 2020).

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte.

Population

Those who answered the questionnaires were the employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region. Since the number of employees was limited, total enumeration was applied.

Data Gathering Instruments

The study adapted validated Hey Group Research (2003) questionnaires on organizational climate and Kuok and Taormina (2017) on work engagement.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the researcher distributed the questionnaires, letters were sent to the presidents of the colleges to request them to allow the researcher to float his questionnaires in their respective institutions. Upon approval, the questionnaires were distributed. In the process of collecting the data, the researcher requested employee representatives to retrieve the data from the respondents before they were submitted to the researcher.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of organizational climate of the schools and Pearson r was used to measure the correlation between organizational climate and work engagement of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Range of Mean Values</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Agree/High
2.51 – 3.50	Somewhat Agree/Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree/Low
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Empirical Data and Analysis

Scientific research is an evidence-based approach and so, is the interpretation of information. Interpretation and analysis are solidly based on the raw data gathered through data-gathering instruments. However, though it is based on raw data, it does not give an absolute answer but only the most like answer based on probability (Rouse, 2020). Based on this concept, this part presents the data and analyses gathered through research questionnaires. The presentation followed the statement of the problem arrangement.

Problem 1: What is the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of:

- 1.1. clarity;*
- 1.2. standards;*
- 1.3. individual responsibility;*
- 1.4. flexibility;*
- 1.5. reward and recognition; and*
- 1.6. team commitment?*

Table 1: Organizational Climate Along with Clarity

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. The strategic direction of the college, as well as the direction of the department and its functions, are clear	3.40	SWA/Moderate
2. The work of different levels in the college fits together to accomplish its mission	3.38	SWA/Moderate
3. Employees are involved in discussing the strategic direction and strategies on how to get there	3.17	SWA/Moderate
4. The employees understand the “whys” of the management’s decision related to employee’s well-being	3.10	SWA/Moderate
5. Policy guidelines are communicated to employees	3.26	SWA/Moderate
6. The lines of authority, as well as roles and responsibilities, are spelled out	3.30	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.27	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

Legend:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Strongly agree/Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Agree/High
2.51 – 3.50	Somewhat agree/Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree/Low
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly disagree/very low

Based on the data gathered, it shows that the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region along with *the clarity dimension* is considered moderate (somewhat agree) which is reflected in its composite mean of 3.27. Even when the items are taken singly, all are rated within the same level of interpretation which is “somewhat agree or moderate”, such as: “the strategic direction of the college, as well as the direction of the department and its functions, are clear (3.40), the work of different levels in the college fits together to accomplish its mission (3.38), employees are involved in discussing the strategic direction and strategies on how to get there (3.17), the employees understand the “whys” of the management’s decision related to employees well-being (3.10), policy guidelines are communicated to employees (3.26), and the lines of authority, as well as roles and responsibilities, are spelled out (3.30). Pijnacker (2019) found in her study that employees who experience clarity are more efficient and effective compared to those who have no clarity about their responsibilities.

Table 2: Organizational Climate Along with Standards

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Employees are given challenging and achievable objectives to accomplish	3.41	SWA/Moderate
2. Employees are involved in determining and monitoring the objectives	3.32	SWA/Moderate
3. The objectives to be achieved are measurable	3.36	SWA/Moderate
4. Effective work behaviors to achieve the objectives are defined	3.31	SWA/Moderate
5. There are prescribed procedures to be followed by employees in carrying out their jobs	3.38	SWA/Moderate
6. Quality standards are clearly defined and understood by employees	3.38	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.36	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

It is the same case with the standards dimension. As reflected in the table, the data reveals that the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region along *the standard dimension* gains a composite mean of 3.36 which is interpreted as “somewhat agree” or “Moderate extent”. Even if the items are taken separately, they all show the same level of assessment which falls within the same interpretation as "somewhat agree or moderate" such as: "employees are given challenging and achievable objectives to accomplish (3.41), involved in determining and monitoring the objectives (3.32), the objectives to be achieved are measurable (3.36), effective work behaviors to achieve the objectives are defined (3.31), there are prescribed procedures to be followed by employees in carrying out their jobs (3.38), and quality standards are clearly defined and understood by employees (3.38).

The evaluation reflects a situation in which the management needs to revisit their tasks on assigning challenging work to employees. Consequently, the employees have no clear idea of achievement. Correspondingly, Ashraf, et.al. (2017) claimed a positive correlation between performance standards and job performance.

Table 3: Organizational Climate along with Responsibility

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. There is a delegation of authority down to the lower level 1 2 3 4 5	3.36	SWA/Moderate
2. Minimum number of interference to ensure autonomy 1 2 3 4 5	3.34	SWA/Moderate
3. Employees are encouraged to cooperate, communicate and practice teamwork on their own 1 2 3 4 5	3.43	SWA/Moderate
4. Provide sufficient room for employees to take initiative and calculated risks 1 2 3 4 5	3.40	SWA/Moderate
5. Holds employees accountable for their performance 1 2 3 4 5	3.40	SWA/Moderate
6. Coaches and counsels employees to manage their problems – solving efforts 1 2 3 4 5	3.35	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.38	SWA/Moderate

Hey Group(2003)

As it is gleaned from the data, it appears that the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of responsibility receives a composite mean of 3.38 which can be interpreted as “somewhat agree on the moderate level”. Even when the items are taken singly, they all reveal the same level of assessment which is "somewhat agree or moderate extent" such as “ delegation of authority (3.36), a minimum number of interference to ensure autonomy (3.34), cooperation, communication and teamwork (3.43), providing sufficient room for employees to take initiative and calculated risks (3.40), holding employees accountable for their performance (3.40), and coaching and counseling employees to manage their problems – solving efforts (3.40).

The management has somehow overlooked delegating responsibilities. Such evaluation indicates that management is hesitant to allow the employees to take control and responsibility for their work. It is noteworthy that Pelit, et.al. (2011) emphasized employees’ satisfaction when they are empowered.

Table 4: Organizational Climate along with Flexibility

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Encourages creativity, experimentation, and independent thinking 1 2 3 4 5	3.38	SWA/Moderate
2. People are not afraid of challenging the norms 1 2 3 4 5	3.34	SWA/Moderate
3. Less bureaucratic steps in the work process 1 2 3 4 5	3.38	SWA/Moderate
4. Be willing to accept other viewpoints that are useful 1 2 3 4 5	3.37	SWA/Moderate
5. Encourages new ideas into practice 1 2 3 4 5	3.38	SWA/Moderate
6. Works for "win-win" rather than "win-lose" solutions 1 2 3 4 5	3.31	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.36	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

The organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region along flexibility obtained a composite mean of 3.36 which is described as "somewhat agree" or moderate extent". Even if they are taken separately, all items manifest the same level of descriptive interpretation which is "somewhat agree or moderate extent" such as "encouraging creativity, experimentation, and independent thinking (3.38), allowing employees to challenge the norms (3.34), lessening the bureaucratic steps in the work process (3.38), willingness to accept other viewpoints that are useful (3.37), encouraging new ideas into practice (3.38) and working for a win-win solution rather than a win-lose solution (3.31).

The management lacks practice in encouraging independent thinking and creativity, allowing employees to challenge the established norms, minimizing bureaucracy to make things fast, encouraging employees to come up with new ideas and practice them, and working on a compromised deal to problems. There is a lack of flexibility from the management side. Davidescu, et.al. (2020) found that flexibility affects the job satisfaction of employees.

Table 5: Organizational Climate Along with Rewards & Recognition

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Provides detailed performance standards to both individual employees and teams/departments	3.29	SWA?Moderate
2. Employees are rewarded on time and performance-based	3.08	SWA/Moderate
3. Advancement opportunities are provided for talented employees	3.18	SWA/Moderate
4. There are non-monetary ways of rewarding individual and group performance	3.29	SWA/Moderate
5. There are opportunities for promotion for those who perform	3.26	SWA/Moderate
6. Management is humble enough to express expressing their positive feedback to employees who accomplish their job well	3.23	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.22	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

In terms of reward and recognition, it garnered a composite mean of 3.22 which can be interpreted as "somewhat agree or moderate extent". Even if the questions are taken separately, they all indicate the same level of assessment which falls within the same descriptive interpretation of "somewhat agree or moderate extent" such as "providing

performance standards (3.28) and rewarding employees based on performance (3.08), advancement opportunity for talented employees (3.18), providing non-monetary ways of rewarding individual and group performance (3.29), promoting those who perform (3.26), and providing positive feedback for employees who accomplished their task (3.23). Baskar (2013) studied the impact of rewards and recognition on employee motivation, and he discovered that rewards and recognition affect motivation and job satisfaction.

Table 6: Organizational Climate Along with Team Commitment

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. There is cooperation among employees to accomplish the goals	3.37	SWA/Moderate
2. Provides ways for people to get to know each other in non-working settings	3.30	SWA/Moderate
3. Identifies team symbols that create a common identity	3.46	SWA/Moderate
4. Sets up systems for cooperation, rather than competition	3.46	SWA/Moderate
5. Ensures that diversity is valued	3.38	SWA/Moderate
6. Structures decision-making to include team input	3.40	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.40	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

Team commitment exists at a moderate extent as shown in the composite mean of 3.40 which is described as "somewhat agree" or moderate extent". Even if the items are taken separately, they all reveal the same descriptive interpretation of "somewhat agree or moderate extent" such as, "cooperation among employees to accomplish the goals (3.37), providing ways for people to get to know each other in non-working settings (3.30), identifying team symbols that create a common identity (3.46), setting up systems for cooperation, rather than competition (3.46), ensuring diversity is valued (3.38) and structuring decision making to include team inputs (3.40). The management somehow fell short of team commitment which could mean as Neiningner, et.al. (2010) emphasized that team commitment affects team performance and altruistic behavior.

Table 7: Organizational Climate Summary Table

Statements	Composite Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Clarity	3.27	SWA/Moderate
Standards	3.36	SWA/Moderate
Responsibility	3.38	SWA/Moderate
Flexibility	3.36	SWA/Moderate
Rewards & Recognition	3.22	SWA/Moderate
Team Commitment	3.40	SWA/Moderate
Overall Mean	3.33	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003) and Drigo Consulting Group (2003).

The overall mean for the organizational climate is 3.33 which is described as somewhat agree or moderate extent. Even after looking into the dimensions of organizational climate, all dimensions of organizational climate are perceived to be moderate such as clarity (3.27), standards (3.36), responsibility (3.38), Flexibility (3.36), rewards and recognition (3.22), and team commitment (3.40).

The evaluation indicates that the management needs to improve the organizational climate along the identified dimensions. Berberoglu’s (2018) study reminds the management that organizational climate affects organizational commitment and performance.

Problem 2: What is the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of

- 2.1. Cognitive engagement;
- 2.2. Affective engagement; and
- 2.3. Conative engagement?

Table 8: Cognitive Work Engagement

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. My mind is often full of ideas about my work	3.63	A/High
2. My mind is fully engaged with my work	3.65	A/High
3. I have an idea about how to perform my work better	3.69	A/High
4. I search for new ways to improve my knowledge related to my work	3.70	A/High
5. My thoughts are fully focused when thinking about my work	3.66	A/High
Composite Mean	3.67	Agree/High

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

The work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of cognitive engagement obtains a composite mean of 3.67 which is described as "agree or high". Even if the items are taken separately, all items are falling within the same range of interpretation which is “agree or high”, such as “their mind is full of ideas about the work (3.63), their mind is fully engaged with their work (3.65), they have the idea about how to perform their work better (3.69), they search for new ways to improve their knowledge related to their work (3.70), and their thoughts are fully focused when they are thinking about their work (3.66).

Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region are highly engaged in their work. They know their work and their mind is fully engaged in their work, have the idea of how to carry out their work, keep on improving their work by getting more new knowledge about their work, and are fully focused on their work.

Table 9: Emotional Work Engagement

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I feel very delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working	3.69	A/High
2. I am excited to do my work	3.70	A/High
3. I feel good about the work that I do	3.66	A/High
4. I am always very enthusiastic to perform my work.	3.74	A/High
5. I feel very happy when I carry out my responsibilities at work.	3.74	A/High
Composite Mean	3.71	Agree/High

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

As presented in the table, the data reveals that the work engagement of the employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region along the emotional dimension gains a composite mean of 3.71 which is described as "agree or high". Even when the items are taken singly, they all are rated within the same level of description which is "agree or high" such as feeling delighted about what they are doing (3.69), feeling excited to do their work (3.70), feeling good with

the work they do (3.66), feeling enthusiastic to perform their work (3.74) and feeling happy when they are carrying out their duties and responsibilities at work (3.74). Employees agree that they are happy with their work.

Table 10: Physical Work Engagement

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. No matter how much I work, I still have a high level of energy	3.61	A/high
2. I have a great deal of stamina for my work	3.64	A/High
3. I have a lot of energy for my work	3.64	A/high
4. I am frequently energized by my work	3.68	A/High
5. Though my work is physically challenging, I am still excited to do it	3.69	A/High
Composite Mean	3.65	Agree/High

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

The work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of physical engagement garnered a composite mean of 3.63 which is interpreted as "agree or high". Even when the items are taken separately, they are all evaluated with the same level of interpretation which is "agree or high" such as "having a high level of energy (3.61), having a great deal of stamina in their work (3.64), having a lot of energy for their work (3.64), feeling energized by their work (3.68), and feeling excited to do their work even though the work is physically challenging (3.69).

The physical work engagement of employees is considered high in terms of their level of energy and stamina invested in their work and they still feel excited to work amid the challenges.

Table 11: Work Engagement Summary Table

Components	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Cognitive engagement	3.67	A/High
Emotional engagement	3.71	A/High
Physical engagement	3.65	A/High
Overall Mean	3.68	Agree/High

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017).

The summary table reveals that overall, the work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is considered high as indicated by its overall mean rating of 3.68. Even when the components are treated individually, they are evaluated within the same range of interpretation which is "agree or high" such as cognitive engagement (3.67), emotional engagement (3.71), and physical engagement (3.65).

The overall mean rating concludes that the work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region has still room for improvement.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between organizational climate and the work engagement of employees?

Table 12: Coefficients of correlation on the Relationship Between the organizational climate and work engagement of employees

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT		WORK ENGAGEMENT		
		Cognitive Work Engagement	Emotional Work Engagement	Physical Work Engagement
Clarity	Pearson Correlation	.567**	.620**	.601**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
Standards	Pearson Correlation	.663**	.712**	.692**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
Responsibility	Pearson Correlation	.590**	.634**	.627**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
Flexibility	Pearson Correlation	.565**	.635**	.619**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
Rewards and Recognition	Pearson Correlation	.454**	.467**	.433**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
Team Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.595**	.639**	.602**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000

**Correlation is significant at a .01 level

A very significant correlation between organizational climate and work engagement at a .01 level of significance exists. Even when the dimensions of organizational climate are taken separately, it shows that all the dimensions of organizational climate such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards, recognition, and team commitment are significantly correlated to different dimensions of work engagement such as cognitive work engagement, emotional work engagement, and physical work engagement.

The findings indicate that the better the organizational climate is, the better the work engagement of employees becomes. In other words, organizational climate is the barometer of work engagement.

Results and Discussion

The main purpose of the study is to determine the correlation between organizational climate and the work engagement of employees. And the result indicates that both variables are correlated. Such a result suggests that managers need to improve the organizational climate of the organization to improve the work engagement of individual employees and even group engagement (Bakis, 2015). Diminishing work engagement can mean many things such as low productivity, quality of product, and profit, and failure to achieve the organizational goals which consequently weakens its competitive advantage (Bakker, Schaufeli, Leiter, & Taris, 2008). Different studies showed that low-level work engagement is one of the main causes of economic problems around the world (Motyka, 2018). In the school context, diminishing teaching engagement can affect the student's academic performance (Cardwell, 2011, Ortiz, 1997) and the school's performance (Ozgenel & Mert, 2019).

The quality of education can never be separated from the work engagement of teachers and employees (Bonney, et.al., 2015). School performance is always correlated with the performance of teachers (Lamas, 2015). Salamat, et.al. (2013) supported this with the statement that students' performance is the result of teachers' performance which is correlated

with the organizational climate. Further, they recommended to the principals determine factors that would promote a better teaching environment. Khan (2019) likewise reiterated this on the effect of organizational climate on the teachers' commitment. This study, therefore, supports the finding of Salamat (2013) that organizational climate enhances teachers' commitment.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study as reflected in the data, the study concludes that the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is considered moderate and the work engagement of employees is considered high. The Pearson r correlation indicated that there is a correlation between organizational climate and work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

The findings of the study contribute to vital discussions among school administrators' school management. It provides important insights into the role of organizational climate to enhance quality education. However, the study also recognized its limits as it only considered six dimensions of organizational climates, such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment. The population of the study was likewise limited to only colleges in the Ilocos Region. It needs to broaden its investigation by adding more dimensions of organizational climate and involving a wider population.

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References

Abun, D., Tabur, M., & Agoot, F. (2017). *Leadership Skills of Administrators of Divine Word Colleges in Region I, the Philippines as Perceived by Employees and Employees' Work Engagement*. IJRDO-Journal of Applied Management Science, 3(12).

Abun, D., Magallanes, Th., Foronda, S.L.G., & Agoot, F. (2019). *Measuring Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction and Frustration and Work Engagement of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region*. International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences (IJELS), 4(2), <https://doi.org/10.22161/ijels.4.2.21>.

Allen, D. K. (2003). *Organizational Climate and Strategic Change in Higher Education: Organizational Insecurity*. Journal of Higher Education, 46(1): 61-92. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1024445024385>

- Ariola, M.M. (2006). *Principles and Methods of Research*. Manila: National Bookstore
- Ashraf, A. M. S., Mazen J. A. S., Samy, S. A.N., Abed, A. M. A., & Youssef, M. A.A. (2017). *The Relationship between Performance Standards and Achieving the Objectives of Supervision at the Islamic University in Gaza*. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems, 1(10), 89-101.
- Bakker, A. B., Schaufeli, W. B., Leiter, M. P., & Taris, T. W. (2008). *Work engagement: An emerging concept in occupational health psychology*. Work & Stress, 22(3), 187-200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678370802393649>
- Balachandran, M & Thomas, I. (2007). *Dimensions of Organizational Climate*. The Psychespace, 1(1), 27-36.
- Bakker, A.B., Albrecht, S., & Leiter, M.P. (2010). *Key questions regarding work engagement*. European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology, 20(1), 4-28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2010.485352>
- Baskar, P. (2013). *A Study on the Impact of Rewards and Recognition on Employee Motivation*. International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR) 4(11),1644.
- Batlolona, J.R. (2018). *Organizational Climate of the School and Teacher Performance Improvement in the 21st Century*. International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR) 7(2),119-126. <https://doi.org/10.21275/ART20179865>
- Berberoglu, A. (2018). *The Impact of Organizational Climate on Organizational Commitment and Perceived Organizational Performance: Empirical Evidence from Public Hospitals*. BMC Health Serv Res 18, 399 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3149-z>
- Bonney, E.a., Amoah, D.F., Micah, S.A. Ahiameny, C., Lemaire, M.B. (2015). *The Relationship between the Quality of Teachers and Pupils' Academic Performance in the STMA Junior High Schools of the Western Region of Ghana*. Journal of Education and Practice, 6(24).
- Cameron, K., & Smart, J. C. (1998). *Maintaining effectiveness amid downsizing and decline in institutions of higher education*. Research in Higher Education, 39, 65-86. <https://doi.org/10.5465/ambpp.1997.4989213>
- Cardwell, M.E., (2011). *Patterns of Relationships Between Teacher Engagement and Student Engagement*. Education Doctoral. Paper 49.
- CEN-CENELEC (2013). *Standards and Your Business*. Retrieved from <https://www.cencenelec.eu>
- Chaudhary, R., Rangnekar, S., & Barua, M.K. (2014). *Organizational Climate, Climate Strength, and Work Engagement*. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences, 133, 291-303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.195>
- Davidescu, A.A., Apostu, S.A., Andreea, P. & Ionut, C. (2020). *Work Flexibility, Job Satisfaction, and Job Performance among Romanian Employees— Implications for Sustainable Human Resource Management*. Sustainability, 12, 6086. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12156086>

- Deniz, M. & Çoban, R. (2016). *Örgütsel iklimin çalışan bağlılığına etkisi ve bir araştırma*. Birey ve Toplum, 6 (12), 49-72
- Dhanisha, M. (2017). *Organizational climate and employee performance in the chemical industry in Kerala: an evaluative study*. Thesis. Department of Commerce and Management Studies, University of Calicut, 2017.
- Drigo Consulting Group (2003). *Creating a Performance Enhancing Organizational Climate*. Retrieved from <https://www.drigoconsultinggroup.com>
- Dulay, S., & Karadag, E. (2015). *The Effect of Leadership on Organizational Climate*. Springer International Publishing Switzerland 2015. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-14908-0_8
- Findikli, M.A. (2015). *Exploring the Consequences of Work Engagement: Relations Among OCB-I, LMX, and Team Work Performance*. Ege Akademik Bakis (Ege Academic Review) 15(2):229-238. <https://doi.org/10.21121/eab.2015217988>
- Foronda, S.G.L. (2010). *The Impact of Leadership Skills, ethics and Values of Administrators toward Organizational Climate of Private Colleges in Region I as Perceived by the Employees*. Unpublished Dissertation. Makati: International Academy of Management and Economics.
- Glick, W.H. (1985). *Conceptualizing and Measuring Organizational and Psychological Climate: Academy of Management Review*. Retrieved from <https://www.managementreview.com>
- Gore, G.W. (2017). *Organizational Clarity*. Team Trek Coaching Group. Retrieved from <https://www.teamtrek.com>
- Heathfield, S. (2019). *The Role of Team Commitment in Team Building. Balance Careers: Human Resources*. Retrieved from <https://www.thebalancecareers.com>
- Hey Group (2003). *Organizational Climate*. Manila: Hay Acquisition Company, Inc
- Hirlak, B., Ebru, G., & Balikci, O. (2018). *The Effects of Organizational Climate on Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Employees' Creativity*. Krakow: Jagiellonian University Institute of Public Affairs
- Hoy, W.K. (2020). *Measuring School Climate, School Climate, and Outcomes, Issues Trends and Controversies*. Retrieved from <https://education.stateuniversity.com>
- Moos, R. (1972). *The Work Environment Scale*. Palo Alto: Social Ecology Laboratory, Department of Psychiatry, Stanford University, 1972.
- James, L.R., & Jones, A.P. (1977). *Psychological and Organizational Climate: Dimensions and Relationships*. Naval Medical Research and Development Command. Retrieved from <https://apps.dtic.mil>

- Kenneth R. Evans & Timothy D. Landry & Po-Chien Li & Shaoming Zou. (1996). *How Sales controls affect job-related outcomes: the role of organizational sales-related psychological climate perceptions*. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-007-0033-5>
- Kenton, W. & Anderson, S. (2020). *Human Resource Planning*. Investopedia. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com>
- Ko, W. & Kang, H. (2019). *Effect of leadership style and organizational climate on employees' food safety and hygiene behaviors in the institutional food service of schools*. Food Science and Nutrition: Willey. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.1056>
- Kopelman, R.E., Guzzo, R.A., & Brief, A. (1990). *The Role of Climate and Culture in Productivity*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers.
- Kuok, A.C.H., & Taormina, R.J. (2017). *Work Engagement: Evolution of the Concept and a New Inventory*. Psychological Thought, 10(2), 262-287. <https://doi.org/10.5964/psyc.v10i2.236>
- LaMarco, N. (2018). *The Advantage of Flexibility in an Organization*. Chron. Retrieved from <https://smallbusiness.chron.com>
- Lamas, H. A. (2015). *School Performance*. Propósitos y Representaciones, 3(1), 313-386.
- Liker, R. (1967). *Human Organizations: Its Management and Values*. New York: McGraw-Hill
- Litwin, G. & Stringer, R. (1967). *Motivation and Organisational Climate*. Boston: Harward University Press
- Ludden, D. (2016). *Are Two Heads Better than One?* Psychology Today. Retrieved from <https://www.psychologytoday.com>
- Maslach, C., & Leiter, M.P. (1997). *The Truth about the Burnout*. San Francisco, CA, USA: Jossey-Bass
- McCombes, Sh. (2020). *Descriptive Research*. Scribbr. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com>
- McLeod, S. (2019). *What are Independent and Dependent Variables?* Retrieved from <https://www.simplypsychology.org>
- Miller, A.R. (2003). *An Analysis of Relationships between the Perceived Organizational Climate and Professional Burnout in Libraries and Computing Centres in West Virginia Public Higher Education Institutions*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation. Huntington: West Virginia Public Higher Education Institutions.
- Motyka, B. (2018). *Employee Engagement and Performance: A Systematic Literature Review*. International Journal of Management and Economics, 54(3), 227-244. <https://doi.org/10.2478/ijme-2018-0018>

Neininger, A., Willenbrock, N.L., Kauffeld, S. & Henschel, A. (2010). *Effects of a team and organizational commitment - A longitudinal study*. Journal of Vocational Behavior 76, 576-579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2010.01.009>

Ortiz, C. (1997). *Relationships between teacher behaviors and student academic engagement in an inner-city preschool*. Masters Theses: University of Massachusetts Amherst

Ozgenel, M. & Mert, P. (2019). *The Role of Teacher Performance in School Effectiveness*. International Journal of Education Technology and Scientific Researches, 4(10),417- 434. <https://doi.org/10.35826/ijets>

Palash, G., & Deepak, T. (2017). *Impact of Organizational Climate on Employee Performance: A Study concerning the Educational Sector of Indore*. International Journal of Research in Commerce & Management. 8(4), 22-25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3149-z>

Pelit, E., Öztürk, Y. & Arslanturk, Y. (2011). *The effects of employee empowerment on employee job satisfaction: A study on hotels in Turkey*. International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management 23(6):784-802. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596111111153475>

Pijnacker, L. (2019). *HR Analytics: Role Clarity Impacts Performance*. Effectory. Retrieved from <https://www.effectory.com>

Putter, L. (2010). *Organizational Climate and Performance*. Unpublished Master Thesis. The Delft University of Technology.

Raja, S., Madhavi, C., & Sankar, S. (2019). *Influence of Organizational Climate on Performance in Manufacturing Industry*. Suraj Punj Journal For Multidisciplinary Research, 9(3), 147-157.

Rose, S. (n.d). *Organizational Flexibility*. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org>

Rousseau, D.M. (2003). *Organizational Climate and Culture*. Retrieved from <https://www.organizationalclimate.com>

Rousseau, D. M. (1988). *The construction of climate in organizational research*. In C. L. Cooper, & I. T. Robertson (Eds.), *International review of industrial and organizational psychology*,3, 139–158). New York: Wiley.

Salamat, N., Samsu, N.J. & Kamalu, N.S.M. (2013). *The Impact of Organizational Climate on teachers' Job Performance*. Educational Research, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5838/erej.2013.21.06>

Sambandam, R. & Chockalingam, M. (2017). *Effect of Organizational Climate on Innovative Work Behavior*. International Journal of Organizational Behaviour and Management Perspectives, 7(3), <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31605.22241>

Schaufeli, W.B., Salanova, M., Gonzalez-Roma, V. & Bakker, A.B. (2002). *The Measurement of Engagement and Burnout: A Two sample confirmatory factor analytic approach*. Journal of Happiness Studies, 3 (1), 71-92. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015630930326>

Stringer, R. (2002). *Motivation and Organizational Climate*. Boston: Harvard Business School Research Press.

Sunarshin, N. & Helmiatin (2017). *Influence of Organizational Climate, Motivation, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance*. Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research, 6 (1).

Thomas, L. (2020). *Independent and Dependent Variables*. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com>

Thomas, A.R. (1976). *The Organizational Climate of Schools*. International Review of Education, 22, 441-463. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00598815>

Waktola, B. (2014). *Organizational Climate and Employees Organizational Commitment*. Asia Europe Journal, Forthcoming. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com>

Western Sydney University Library (2017). *Literature Review Purpose*. Retrieved from <https://westernsydney.edu.au>

Wilkinson, D. & Birmingham, P. (2003). *Using Research Instruments A Guide for Researchers*. London: Routledge Falmer.

Wilson, M. (2012). *The One Thing to Win at the Game of Business*. Retrieved from <https://www.under30ceo.com>

Woolley, A. W., Aggarwal, I., & Malone, T. W. (2015). *Collective intelligence and group performance*. Current Directions in Psychological Science, 24, 420-424. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721415599543>

Yuan, Ch. & Lee, Ch. (2011). *Exploration of a construct model linking leadership types, organization culture, employee performance, and leadership performance*. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 25 (2011) 123 – 136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.534>

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